

SUPPORT NEEDS FOR CAPACITY BUILDING OF SMALL AGRICULTURAL MACHINERY MANUFACTURERS IN BANGLADESH

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Abstract

Survey in four districts of Bangladesh namely Mymensingh, Kishorganj, Sherpur and Netrokona were carried out to assess the support needs for capacity building of small agricultural machinery manufacturing workshops. Farmers expressed their confidence on the presently available locally made agricultural machines and equipment by small machinery manufacturers within the country and eager to adopt appropriate machines to few labour intensive and time consuming crop production activities. From the viewpoint of sustaining agricultural production in the country, capacity building of small agricultural machinery manufacturers is a crucial need of the time. The volume of production of agricultural machinery is increasing and different types of machinery are being made locally but most of the agricultural machinery manufacturing workshops are in primary stage. They faced many technical, financial, environmental and so many problems and it is necessary to support local agricultural machinery manufacturing workshops to overcome these problems and to build their capacity. Suggestions in this context are proposed to minimize the problems and to build their capacity.

Key words: Capacity building, agricultural, machinery, manufacturers

Introduction

Bangladesh agriculture was mostly traditional with a very limited mechanical intervention. At present farmers are becoming conversant with mechanical interventions such as power tiller, shallow and deep tube wells, push-pull weeder, hand and knapsack sprayers; pedal, open-drum and close-drum threshers; rice hullers etc. (Sarker, 2000). Generally farm machinery and implements are manufactured by the industrialized countries. Most of the developing countries like Bangladesh import these machineries from industrialized countries. These machines are expensive and their operating cost is high. If imported machinery could be manufactured locally and could be adapted to our agro-ecological conditions at lower price, local manufacturing workshops would promote employment facilities and help poverty alleviation.

Locally made machines in Bangladesh are Seeder, weeder, centrifugal pump, turbine pump, treadle pump (pedal pump), diesel engines, paddy hulling/polishing, trailer for tractor, rice huller (small), sprayers, threshers, traditional hand tools, accessories of LLP & STW, traditional hand loom, wooden plough, animal drawn vehicles etc. (Hasan, 1992).

Mechanization creates technical know how among the people and sufficient job opportunities for local skilled and unskilled labour. For right planning in mechanization, necessary information about Agricultural Machinery Manufacturing Workshops (AMMW) is important. It is difficult to make policy about mechanization in absence of right information. A study is required to provide latest information about support needs for capacity building of small agricultural machinery manufacturers. As such this research work was undertaken to assess the type of support needs for capacity building of small Agricultural Machinery Manufacturers in Bangladesh.

Methodology

The study was based on the field survey, where primary data were collected by questionnaire from individual manufacturer. Although, agricultural machinery manufacturers are situated all over the country, four district towns namely Mymensingh, Kishorganj, Sherpur and Netrokona were selected where farm machinery manufacturing industries are concentrated and maximum industry are established.

In Mymensingh all authorized agricultural machinery manufacturers are located in and around district towns and these are situated at Tangail Road (Muktagacha), Saheb Ali Bazar (Muktagacha), and Dhaka Road (Sahra). Data were collected from 4 workshops located in Mymensingh, 15 workshops located at Akrapur, Karimganj and Stadium market in Kishorganj district, 6 workshops located at Teen Ani Bazar, Jhinaigachhi Bus Stand, Taragonj (Nolitabari), Hospital Road (Nolitabari), Isibpur (Nokla) of Sherpur district and 7 workshops located at New Court Road, Choto Bazar, Shamgonj Bazar, Madan Bazar (Madan) Pathar Ghat, Station Road in Netrokona district.

The draft interview schedules were prepared according to the objectives of the study. Primary information was collected with the draft schedules from the study area. The answers, which obtained from the manufacturers were carefully checked and desired correction, modification and addition were incorporated in the schedules and afterwards information were collected carefully.

Results and Discussion

Support needs in Management of Organization

Table 1 shows the management status of the different Agricultural Machinery Workshops. From the study about 100%, 75%, 100% and 88% of the agricultural machinery workshops respectively in Mymensingh, Kishorganj, Sherpur and Netrokona

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are managed by the owner themselves. Employed manager manages only about 25% and 12% of the machinery workshops in Kishorganj and Netrokona respectively.

Almost all machinery manufacturers want better training to improve their management skills. But only 25% and 12% of the manufacturers in Kishorganj and Netrokona are not eager to receive better management technique to improve their business. Their management technique is sufficient enough for their workshop. Most of the agricultural machinery manufacturers expressed need for support from different Government Organizations, NGO's and Institutions to improve their skills in management for their business.

Support needs in Input Supply

Table 2 shows that shortage of raw materials. Cost of raw materials, Low quality of raw materials is a serious problem in Agricultural Machinery Workshops. Several manufacturers produce farm machinery using low quality materials resulting poor performance of the product. High transport cost and unhealthy political environment is also a serious problem for agricultural machinery workshops in different districts. These contribute to the increase of price of the locally made machinery than that of imported machinery, which discourages the local manufacturer to manufacture farm machinery.

Agricultural Machinery Workshops in few districts have their own cooperatives or Trade associations by which they can overcome these problems. Agricultural Machinery Workshops in Kishorganj buy their raw materials through cooperatives. As a result they can buy the raw materials in cheaper price. In this way they can also reduce transport cost and overcome the unhealthy political environment. To overcome these problems they also expressed need for support from different Government and Non-Government organizations.

Support needs in Market access

Most of the AMMW supply their products to the local or regional market and very few in the whole

country. Almost all agricultural machinery workshops supply their products to the farmers directly and/or through order system. The study reveals that 75%, 75%, 100% and 75% of the manufacturer in Mymensingh, Kishorganj, Sherpur and Netrokona respectively determine the price of their products with 15-20% profit.

According to some agricultural machinery manufacturers, few unauthorized enterprises manufacture same type of implements of below standard quality and sell at low price. They also face unscrupulous business behaviour from some large business enterprises. This is very much alarming for the development of local agricultural machinery manufacturers. This is why Government should take necessary steps and the agricultural machinery manufacturers should make cooperatives or trade associations to overcome these problems.

Agricultural machinery manufacturers can increase the sale of their product with lower price, advertising, machinery hire facilities, etc.

Agricultural machinery manufacturers think that the custom tariff rate on imported agricultural equipment should be fixed at higher level so that the price of imported equipment remains higher than the locally produced equipment for the same quality. Public and private sectors should take an initiative for extensive farm level demonstration of farm machinery. Government incentives should be offered for manufacturing as well as purchasing locally made machines by farmers.

Support needs in Technology or Product development

Production facility is one of the determining factors of the capacity of agricultural machinery manufacturing workshop. Number of machineries are present in the agricultural machinery manufacturing workshops are given in Table 4.

Table 1. Management technique & Support needs in Management

		Mymensingh No. (%)	Kishorganj No. (%)	Sherpur No. (%)	Netrokona No. (%)
Managed by whom	Manage by own	4(100)	9(75)	6(100)	7(88)
	Manage by manager	0(0)	3(25)	0(0)	1(12)
	Manage by others	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)
Training for better management	Employ Manager	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)
	Trained on Management	4(100)	9(75)	6(100)	7(88)
	Not necessary	0(0)	3(25)	0(0)	1(12)

Table 2. Problems in Input Supply

Problems	Mymensingh No. (%)	Kishorganj No. (%)	Sherpur No. (%)	Netrokona No. (%)
Lack of raw materials	1(25)	4(33)	3(50)	3(38)
High cost of raw materials	2(50)	4(33)	3(50)	4(50)
Low quality of raw materials	1(25)	3(25)	2(33)	3(38)
High transport cost	2(50)	4(33)	2(33)	3(38)
Unhealthy political environment	1(25)	4(33)	3(50)	3(38)

Values in the parenthesis indicate the percentage

Capacity building of small agricultural machinery manufacturers

Table 3. Support needs in Market access

		Mymensingh	Kishorganj	Sherpur	Netrokona
		No. (%)	No. (%)	No. (%)	No. (%)
Marketing system	Farmers directly	4(100)	9(75)	6(100)	6(75)
	Dealers	0(0)	1(8)	0(0)	0(0)
	Order system	4(100)	9(75)	6(100)	6(75)
	From showroom	0(0)	3(25)	0(0)	0(0)
Profit	(10-15)%	1(25)	2(17)	0(0)	0(0)
	(15-20)%	3(75)	9(75)	6(100)	6(75)
	(20-25)%	0(0)	1(8)	0(0)	2(25)
	Improve Quality	2(50)	9(75)	4(66)	4(50)
To promote sale	Lower price	2(50)	6(50)	2(33)	4(50)
	Advertise	3(75)	4(33)	3(50)	6(75)
	Rent machinery facilities	1(25)	3(25)	3(50)	4(50)

Table 4. Production facility of A.M.M.W in studied area

Machine Type	Mymensingh	Kishorganj	Sherpur	Netrokona
	No. (%)	No. (%)	No. (%)	No. (%)
Lathe	4(100)	10(83)	6(100)	8(100)
Shaper	1(25)	3(25)	2(33)	3(37)
Drilling machine	4(100)	12(100)	6(100)	8(100)
Grinding machine	2(50)	8(67)	3(50)	6(75)
Milling machine	1(25)	8(67)	3(50)	4(50)
Welding machine	4(100)	11(91)	6(100)	8(100)
Power press	0(0)	2(17)	0(0)	0(0)
Air compressor	0(0)	3(25)	0(0)	2(25)
Sheet metal bender	0(0)	4(33)	1(16)	2(25)
Spray painting	1(25)	4(33)	1(16)	2(25)
Mechanical saw	1(25)	6(50)	2(33)	4(50)

Table 5. Support needs in finance

		Mymensingh	Kishorganj	Sherpur	Netrokona
		No. (%)	No. (%)	No. (%)	No. (%)
Sources of capital	Elder brother/ close relatives	2(50)	8(67)	3(50)	6(75)
	Bank savings	0(0)	1(8)	0(0)	0(0)
	Bank loan	0(0)	1(8)	0(0)	0(0)
	NGOs	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	1(12)
	Money Lender	2(50)	2(16)	3(50)	2(25)
Wants financial support from	Government	4(100)	10(83)	6(100)	8(100)
	Credit facility	4(100)	9(75)	5(83)	6(75)
	NGO	2(50)	6(50)	4(67)	6(75)
	Low interest rate	3(75)	12(100)	6(100)	8(100)

Values in the parenthesis indicate the percentage

Number of workshop machineries per agricultural machinery manufacturing workshops in the study area was very small. They need more machines to increase their capacity. But due to lack of capital, infrastructure, skilled personnel, lack of technical know-how and other facilities they are not able to build their capacity. Maximum employees in the study area have no academic certificate. They have no training from any formal training institute. There is no agricultural engineer in any workshop in the study area. The quality of machine is not also satisfactory.

Technical Assistance by the government and NGOs or private sectors is needed for providing skill and knowledge related to modern agricultural technologies manufacture. Training centers at local level must be set up by the government, NGO and private sectors to provide training to the workers employed by manufacturers to build up their

capacity. Training on nominal cost should be provided by the GO, NGO and private sectors to get more workers to enroll.

Support needs in Finance

Financial problem is faced by all of the agricultural machinery manufacturing workshop in whole of surveyed area. This problem becomes serious during peak production season. Table 5 shows that the sources of money for their business, and the trading arrangements of their business.

It was observed that maximum workshops in the study area needed financial support from Government, NGOs, Banks and other private organizations for the capacity building. Government and NGO could play an important rule for developing credit system which could help for purchasing the raw materials.

Table 6. Policies needed for machinery manufacturers

Policies needed	Mymensingh No. (%)	Kishorganj No. (%)	Sherpur No. (%)	Netrokona No. (%)
Customs tariff rate on local agril. equipment should be selected at low level	2(50)	9(75)	6(100)	7(87)
Double taxation should be removed	4(100)	10(83)	5(83)	6(75)
Government incentives should be offered on manufacturing and purchasing locally made machines	4(100)	12(100)	6(100)	8(100)
Establishment of procurement policies	2(50)	10(83)	4(67)	5(62)
Development of sub contracting system	2(50)	6(50)	3(50)	5(62)
Complexity of taking bank loan should be removed	4(100)	12(100)	6(100)	8(100)

Values in the parenthesis indicate the percentage

Table 7. Problems in Business Environment

Problems	Mymensingh No. (%)	Kishorganj No. (%)	Sherpur No. (%)	Netrokona No. (%)
Transportation	0(0)	3(25)	0(0)	3(37)
Interruption of electric supply	4(100)	10(83)	4(67)	7(87)
Warehouse problem	1(25)	4(33)	2(33)	3(37)
Marketing problem	2(50)	3(25)	3(50)	4(50)
Unethical business behaviour from other unauthorized enterprises	2(50)	3(25)	3(50)	3(37)
Unstable political environment	2(50)	4(33)	4(67)	3(37)

Values in the parenthesis indicate the percentage

Support needs in Policy

Agricultural mechanization policy is an essential part of overall agricultural development. The main objective of the national policy for agricultural mechanization is to increase agricultural productivity and decrease production costs of agricultural commodities in order to be competitive in the event of worldwide free market economy. Unfortunately, there exists no specific agricultural mechanization policies and strategies in the country. The subsequent governments have taken some short-term measures to cope with the increasing demand of agricultural machines among the farming community. The measures included waiver of import tax on essential agricultural machinery and equipment, budgetary provision for subsidy on agricultural machinery and other crop production inputs, and agricultural credit facilities at reasonable interest rate for the farmers from government, non-government and private financial institutions (The Daily Star, 11 June 2004).

Table 6 shows the different policies or regulations that are needed for the agricultural machinery manufacturers in the study area to support their business.

Support needs in Business Environment

Congenial business environment is essential for capacity building of agricultural machinery manufacturers in Bangladesh. Almost all agricultural machinery manufacturers face some problems in business environment that are shown in Table 7.

Conclusions

Maximum agricultural machinery manufacturing workshops in the study areas were not technically well equipped. The qualities of machines produced were not satisfactory and there was no sufficient quality control facility. Almost all agricultural machinery manufacturers need supports in capacity building within workshops as well as in developing healthy business environment for quality machinery production.

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